

Articles

Dalit conflicts in Bihar.

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Abstract

The objective of the researcher is to study "Dalit conflicts in Bihar." Due to discrimination in Hindu religion a large number of Dalit Hindus converted to Islam, Sikhism, Christianity etc. Dalits have come into conflict with the upper castes because they are no longer willing to remain subjugated to them. The role of revolutionary parties is especially significant in the rise of Dalit consciousness and this gives rise to conflicts between Dalits and the upper castes.

Key words: Caste Dalit, Harijan, Scheduled Caste, untouchable, sena

Introduction

The word "Dalit" has been derived from [Sanskrit](#) means "ground", "suppressed", "crushed" or "broken to pieces". The father of the nation Gandhiji coined the word "Harijan" means "Children of God" to identify the Dalits. But this term is now considered derogatory when used to describe Dalits. In addition the terms "Scheduled castes and scheduled tribes" (SC/ST) are the official terms used in Indian government documents to identify former "untouchables" and tribes. India's caste system assigns individuals a certain hierarchical status according to Hindu beliefs. Traditionally, there are four

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principal castes (divided into many sub-categories) and one category of people who fall outside the caste system—the Dalits. A group of people traditionally regarded as untouchable is designated as "Dalit". Dalits are a mixed population, consisting of numerous social groups; they speak a variety of languages and practice a multitude of religions. There are many different names proposed for defining this group of people, including Panchamas i.e. fifth varna and Asprushya ("untouchables"). In 2001, the proportion of Dalit population was 16.2 percent of India's total population. The Dalit population is broadly distributed across Indian states and districts. In 2001, the state of Panjab had the highest proportion of its population as Dalit, at about 29 percent, and the state of Mizoram had the lowest at nearly zero. The government of India recognises and protects them as Scheduled Castes. The term Dalit has been interchangeably used with term Scheduled Castes, and these terms include all historically discriminated communities of India out-caste and Untouchables.

The origins of the caste system

The word Dalit—literally translating to "oppressed" or "broken"—is generally used to refer to people who were once known as "untouchables", those belonging to castes outside the fourfold Hindu Varna system. According to the 2001 census, there are some 167 million Dalits (referred to in the census as "Scheduled Castes") in India alone, though there are tens of millions in other South Asian countries, as well. The caste system finds its origin in functional groupings, called varnas, which have their origins in the Aryan society of ancient northern India. In their creation myth, four varnas are said to have emanated from the Primeval Being. The Creator's mouth became the Brahman priests, his two arms formed the Rajanya warriors and kings, his two thighs formed the Vaishya landowners and merchants, and from his feet were born the Shudra artisans and servants (Kelkar, 1979). Later, there developed a so-called "fifth" varna: the Untouchables. This caste system became fixed and hereditary with the emergence of Hinduism and its beliefs of pollution and rebirth. The Laws of Manu

(Manusmitri), which date roughly to the 3rd century A.D.—and parts of which form the Sanskrit syllabus of graduation studies in Gujarat even today—preach the and total impunity of Brahmins. Those from the “lowest” castes are told that their place in the caste hierarchy is due to their sins in a past life. Vivid punishments of torture and death are assigned for crimes such as gaining literacy or insulting a member of a dominant caste. Among the writings of Hindu religious texts, the Manusmitri is undoubtedly the most authoritative one, legitimizing social exclusion and introducing absolute inequality as the guiding principle of social relations.

Dalits and religion

The Sachar Committee report of 2006 revealed that scheduled castes and tribes of India are not limited to the religion of Hinduism. The 61st round Survey of the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) found that 90% of the Buddhists, one-third of the Sikhs, and one-third of the Christians in India belonged to the notified scheduled castes or tribes of the Constitution.

Religion	Scheduled Caste	Scheduled Tribe	Total
Buddhism	90%	7.40%	97%
Christianity	9%	33%	42%
Sikhism	31%	0.9%	32%
Hinduism	22%	9%	31%
Jainism	–	2.6%	2.6%

Dalit conflicts in Bihar

So long as the Dalits are ignorant and submissive, they have no problem from the Hindu castes. But with rapid changes in their life style and awareness of the fact that they are also human beings and the state has adopted certain special measures for their protection, the social situation has changed. This rapid transformation has given some of them courage

sanctity of the varnas and uphold the principles of gradation and rank. They refer to the impurity and servility of the outcastes, while affirming the dominance and they are prepared to challenge the Hindu caste. Water is an essential requirement of human beings. Wherever it is available, all people without reference to religion, cast and class should have right to use it. But even here the untouchables are discriminated. There are few types of sources, namely tank, pond, river, well and tap. There is a big history in this country which narrates the total prohibition or partial prohibition imposed on the Dalits by the caste Hindus. The Dalits were not allowed to take water from these sources since the water gets polluted or contaminated when once the Dalit touches the water. The tradition well established in the Indian society is that the caste Hindus can do anything with the Dalit women and none should question them. If on the other hand, the Dalit youths tease a Hindu girl, this leads to serious action from the caste- Hindus. Retaliation is the first course of action. Bonded labour is abolished by law on paper. But in reality it is very alive. These labourers are almost members of the Scheduled Castes. Harassment is still a common feature. But what happens then? Does the Hindu caste tolerate this? How do they react to the challenges? The result is conflicts in the form of Caste Militias, Naxalites and Ranvir Sena etc.

Caste Militias

In 1969 the upper caste Rajputs formed a Militia named the Kuer Sena. In 1979 the Kunwar Sena of Rajputs was formed, it disintegrated in 1986. In 1988 the Sunlight Sena dominated by Rajputs came into existence. The Brahmarshi Sena represented by Bhumihars before the creation of Ranvir Sena was launched at a conference at Patna in 1981. The Samajwadi Krantikari Sena formed of Rajputs was founded. The Bhumihar dominated Savarna Liberation Front also known as Diamond Sena came into existence in 1990. Like the upper castes, backward caste landlords

have cultivated private militias for protection. The Bhoomi Sena was formed by backward caste Kurmis. The Lorik Sena was formed by the Yadav landlords of Jahanabad district, while the Kisan Sangh is a militia of middle caste landlords. The Militias were responsible for many massacres. On 27th September` 1991 the Diamond Sena beheaded seven Dalit and tribal labourers in Sawanbiga village in Jahanabad district.

Naxalites

In 1968 after Naxalbari uprising in West Bengal, various Marxist- Leninist factions began calling for a militant peasant struggle against upper caste domination in Bihar (Khan, 2005). Throughout their history, Naxalite groups have engaged in attacks on civilians and abuses that directly violate international humanitarian law. The Naxalites actively recruited Dalit and lower caste peasants into their militant struggle. By 1998, Naxalite groups were operational in thirty six out of fifty four districts of the then Bihar. The Naxalite groups are dominated by the Maoist Communist Centre (MCC), the Communist Party of India (Marxist-Leninist) Party Unity, and the Communist Party of India (Marxist-Leninist) ,(CPI (M-L)) Liberation. In 1977 CPI (M-L) Liberation moved away from an emphasis on "annihilation of individual class enemies" to an attempt at organising mass peasant movements through Kisan Sabha (peasant organisations). In 1982 the group decided to enter parliamentary politics under the banner of the Indian People's Front (IPF). Through IPF won one parliamentary seat in 1989, seven members in 1989 and six members in 1995 to the Bihar state assembly. These political movements have provided an organised platform for growing resistance to the still prevalent norms of 'untouchability'. Dalits have demanded equal treatment in temple festivals, have refused to carryout ritually demeaning tasks, have demanded access to public water sources, and have claimed an equal share of public goods and village properties. While CPI (M-L) Liberation has pursued a parliamentary path, Party Unity and Maoist Communist Centre have spearheaded a militant grassroots movement. In turn that has been targeted by Ranvir Sena attacks. Both MCC and Party Unity are banned

underground movements. The MCC was responsible for the killing of at least fifty four upper caste Rajput community members in Dalelchak Baghaura in May 1987. The incident was the worst massacre in the state until the Ranvir Sena killing of sixty one Dalits in Laxmanpur Bathe on 1st December` 1997. MCC was also responsible for slitting the throats of forty four upper caste farmers in Bara village on 12th February 1992. Thirty six died on the spot and one died in the hospital. According to press reports, 295 people were killed in Naxalite violence in 1995, 436 in 1996 and 424 in 1997. On 11th August 1998, CPI (M-L) Party Unity merged with CPI (M-L) and formed People's War Group (PWG). Like MCC and Party Unity, PWG advocated the use of violence against the upper castes.

Ranvir Sena

The Ranvir Sena was founded by upper caste Bhumihars in Belaur village of Bhojpur district in 1994. It first made international headlines in July 1996 with its attack on Bathani Tola in Bhojpur district of Bihar. In the incident 19 Dalits and Muslims, mostly women and children died. Sixty members of Sena reportedly descended on the village and set twelve houses on fire. Using lathis, swords and firearms the attackers continued the onslaught for two and half hours. The attack was in retaliation for the earlier killing of nine Bhumihars in Nadhi village in Bhojpur district by the CPI (M-L). Since its inception, the Ranvir Sena has been implicated in killings, rapes and lootings in the villages of Belaur, Ekwari, Chandi, Nanaur, Narhi, Sarathau, Haibaspur, Laxmanpur Bathe, Shankarbiga and Narayanpur. On 22nd April` 1996 the Sena gunned down five members of a marriage party in Nanaur village. The victims were CPI (M-L) supporters. In 1997 the Sena killed three Dalits in Jehanabad district for raising their voice against the rape of a Dalit girl by upper cast youths. Sena membership is divided by districts and that all districts have a commander. The Sena is present in Jahanabad, Aurangabad, Bhojpur, Rohtas, Gaya, Bahuwaban, Baxar, Bhagalpur and Muzafarpur districts. In the districts of central Bihar,

over 400 people were killed between 1995 and 1997 in large scale massacres committed by Ranvir Sena. The Ranvir Sena even has a program of life insurance: "their families get paid Rs. 100,000/- if they get killed in a massacre, in the line of duty" (Shinde, 2005).

Conclusion

The practice of untouchability is the greatest curse of the Indian social system. Nowhere in the world and at no point of time in its history was this type of practice witnessed. However, there has been lot of changes in the attitudes of the Hindu caste because of the struggle of Dr. Ambedkar and Gandhiji. Anti-Dalit prejudices exist in fringe groups, such as the extremist militia Ranvir Sena, largely run by upper-caste landlords in Indian state of Bihar. They oppose equal treatment of Dalits and have resorted to violent means to suppress the Dalits. The Ranvir Sena is considered a terrorist organisation by the government of India. On the other Naxalism, largely run by Dalits to counter the Ranvir Sena. Another political issue is over the affirmative- action measures taken by the government towards the upliftment of Dalits through quotas in government jobs and university admissions. About 8% of the seats in the National and State Parliaments are reserved for Scheduled Caste and Tribe candidates, a measure sought by B. R. Ambedkar and other Dalit activists in order to ensure that Dalits would obtain a proportionate political voice.

Since 1950, India has enacted and implemented many laws and social initiatives to protect and improve the socio-economic conditions of its Dalit population. By 1995, of all jobs in India, 17.2 percent of the jobs were held by Dalits, greater than their proportion in Indian population. In 1997, India democratically elected K. R. Narayanan, a Dalit, as the nation's President. The quality of life of Dalit population in India, in 2001, in terms of metrics such as access to health care, life expectancy, education attainability, access to drinking water, housing, etc. was statistically similar to overall population of modern India. In India's most populous

state, Uttar Pradesh, Dalits have revolutionised politics and have elected a popular Dalit chief minister named Mayawati. Smti. Meera Kumar a dalit woman elected as speaker of 15th parliament of India. In 2014, Sri Jitan Ram Manjhi a popular Dalit leader elected as Chief minister of Bihar.

Bibliography

Kelkar, S. (1979). *The History of Caste in India*. New Delhi:: Cosmo Publications.

Khan, M. A. (2005). *Human rights and the dalits*. : . New Delhi: Uppal Publishing House.

Shinde, P. K. (2005). *Dalits and human rights..* Delhi: : Isha Books.